

THE ROLE OF TRADITIONAL AND MODERN COLORS IN ARTISTIC DECORATION IN THE DIRECTION OF POTTERY

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Abstract. In the process of creating this article the more clay is cooked, the better the quality of the pottery.

The main weapon in pottery is the Potter's hammer, the master prepares dishes in it and shapes them gives. Prepared dishes are dried and heated in humdon. Types of dishesumdons may also be diverse (large-small). Glazing dishesonce glazed, it is heated once again in humdon. As a rule, Potters are known disheswill specialize in production (e.g. kosagar, kozagar, koshinpaz,the Tander et al.Pottery, pottery remains and passes through avlot.After all, it is the task of the younger generation to advance it.

Keywords: architecture, enlightenment, art, mausoleum, Sha'jara, structure, symmetry.

РОЛЬ ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ И СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ЦВЕТОВ В ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОМ УКРАШЕНИИ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ГОНЧАРНОГО ИЗДЕЛИЯ

Аннотация. В процессе создания данной статьи, чем больше глины варится, тем лучше качество керамики.

Главным оружием в гончарстве является гончарный молот, в нем мастер готовит блюда и придает им форму. Подготовленные блюда сушат и нагревают в хумдоне. Виды блюд-шумдонов также могут быть разнообразными (большими-маленькими). Глазурованная посуда после того, как глазурована, снова нагревается в хамдоне. Как правило, гончары специализируются на изготовлении известной посуды (например, косагар, кодагар, кошинпаз, тандер и др. Гончарное дело, керамика остается и проходит через авлот. Ведь задача молодого поколения – продвигать ее.

Ключевые слова: архитектура, просвещение, искусство, мавзолей, Шаджара, структура, симметрия.

Introduction: Currently according to the method of artistic decoration, shape and preparation methods there are the following pottery schools: Fergana (main centers-Rishton,Furumsaroy), Bukhara-Samarkand (main centers-Samarkand, Urgut, Gijduvan,Uba), Khwarazm (main centers — Madir, Kattabogh villages), Tashkent. Each the school has its own development and creative principles, leading centers and Masters,in addition to having unique characteristics, the main artistic commonality is kept. The craft of pottery is divided into several areas. For example, the Masters of Fergana divided into kosagar, kozagar, lagansoz, togorasoz, khurmachi, khumchi occupations.

Ceramic and the dishes themselves are not Glazed, Glazed and divided into porcelain items. Household items for non-glazed dishes-Khum, khumcha, pitcher, obdasta, ovenin.

They were made by hand by combining pieces of ribbon-like clay. Little wood the areas united by the tool are polished.

Results : Lead glaze and yellowish-green, brown paints occupy an important place in the resonant elegance of the objects of the Bukhara-Samarkand pottery school. Plant-like patterns lead in the decoration of objects prepared based on the traditions of the "afrosib pottery", geometric patterns, images of animals are little used.

They are mainly used in Gjiiduvan pottery. While gyzhduvan, Shahrisabz Masters work in moyqalam, Urgut, Denov masters use drawing patterns a lot. The brothers Alisher and Abdullah Narzullayev from gijduwon work effectively in preserving, developing and conveying traditions to successors.

The responsible stage of making an item in pottery is the pattern on the item and mystery is a process of giving. In particular, Rishton Masters items more from the mystery of lojuvari widely used, blue-rainbow, green-rainbow, brown or brown-purple those embroidered with colors such as.

Patterns are often derived from plant islimium in appearance, there were variations. Elegant if ordinary items are glazed with colorless alkali the objects made were glazed with tin-lead tin or lead.

In the Valley, Potters are apricot glue to blue, yellow, red, black, blue, white and other colors, even mixing flour, sand, iron powder, they painted the dishes in colors. Bottles some masters also made patterns using a mold. Usually in pencil style items given a patterned blue or brown hue like pumpkin, carrots, beets embroidered through molds made of vegetables. Required materials: ceramic, tray, plaster, bisser-stones, oil paints, disperserspains, cyst, foil paper, glue types and other materials.

Order of work:

1. We paint the ceramic surface white with an emulsion.
2. The pattern is transplanted to the surface of the container-using a pencil;
3. Decoration with Bisser and stones is glued step by step;
4. Gluing the plaster to the edge of the ceramic using a cloth is performed;
5. Finishing-selected depending on the type of item;
6. The ceramic edge is colored with an emulsion;
7. Apply varnish to the surface, paint glossy disperses without hardening varnish, or sprinkle with dice. This technology is embodied in national types of crafts will be created. Such as pottery, embroidery, handrails and work with decorative stones it consists of a set of trades. The pattern worked on the pottery is technological below

listed in the map.

.Masters place a simplified form or some parts of animals at the bottom of the dishes ("tail eagle", "murgi safid", "owl", "guli Peacock", etc.), which are striking in that the forms look like a floral pattern. Features such as the feeling of novelty, the free treatment of traditional forms are clearly visible in the items created by the narzullaevs.

Bukhara-Samarkand pottery school is distinguished from other schools by the presence of a center where cera. In the 80s of the 20th century, work in pottery centers became somewhat muted.

The focus on traditional values in Uzbekistan in the 1990s ensured the development of this sector. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the exhibition of traditional works of Applied Art (Republic

fair) was founded. The 1st Republic fair in 1995 (dedicated to the 50th anniversary of the UN) was attended by representatives of all the pottery schools. From The Masters R. Zuhurov (Denov),

Conclusion: In place of the conclusion, it can be said that the preparation of souvenirs there are many types, the technology of their preparation is different. Souvenirs interest in Applied Art in students through training, creative mood, to work inspire motivation, build labor skills and build your national values forms qualities such as respect and appreciation.

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